

OCCASIONAL TRANSFORMATION PHENOMENON AND ITS EXPRESSIONS IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about the occasional transformation phenomenon and its expressions in phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages. It includes annotation, keywords, introduction, main part, conclusion and references.

Problems of occasional transformation of phraseology are also included in the science of stylistics, because the main purpose of transformation is to achieve a certain stylistic effect. In linguistics, the structural changes of phraseology, and the system of transformations in general, have not yet been fully studied, both in terms of vernacular and casual. Phraseological units are both oral and written and occasional. That is, the usual meaning of a phraseological unit is reflected in its dictionary. Has a complex semantic content. For phraseological units, some connotative units in their composition are also important. All of these factors are the

context of phraseological units, which can be the basis for studying them.

Russian linguist A.V. Kunin was one of the first to study occasional features.

A.Mamatov, a researcher of phraseological units, explains that the proverb in Uzbek language is enriched by the addition of the phrases "Jon chekmasang jonona qayda , toqqa chiqmasang do'lona qayda" , "Uylanmasang , qaynona qayda" ". Occasional meaning is an artificial and one-time expression that is not specific to the linguistic meaning of a lexeme, but is the result of the speech situation of an individual (author) that gives a new "color" to the content of the lexeme. The concept of transformation is the process of translating

from one language to another. It is individual and can only be understood in context.

Consider the following example:

To make "Pashshadan fil yasamoq iborasi" is to know the meaning of the phrase "to make a tragedy out of a simple little thing." we can see that the meaning is intensified and exaggerated. So, we can know from this phrase that the phenomenon of "Occasional Transformation" is a phenomenon that reinforces and exaggerates the meaning of a phrase in a particular language and is used only once by the author

Occasional meaning is a lexeme that is not specific to the meaning of the language,

Lexical monosemia (Greek: monos - "one" + semia - "sign") -

that a lexeme has only one meaning. For example, Uzbek rice

The lexeme means "grain of rice", eternal the lexeme means "eternal, permanent," and the night lexeme means "day of the day."

from sunset to sunrise, from evening to dawn »

means These lexemes have no other meaning.

The phenomenon of monosemia is also considered a monolith in Uzbek linguistics referred to. More than one term, newly created or otherwise

to the period of initial use of newly mastered lexemes from the language

belongs to: a rectangle (math. term), a dome (newly created lexeme), supermarket (newly mastered word), etc.

Newly created or newly mastered lexemes from another language

under the influence of various linguistic and non-linguistic factors over time can become words.

Famous nouns are also conditionally included in the series of monoscanthic lexemes is added. In the processes of occasional transformation of phraseological units, the strengthening of the semantics of phraseological units is a common phenomenon, which is associated with such a feature of phraseological units as expressiveness. Expressiveness, V.M. Mokienko, - in addition to relative stability, reproducibility, and holistic meaning - is a categorical feature of phraseological units. The scholar argues that 'complementarity' transforms phraseology into a system of expressive plan units due to the complexity of phraseological semantics, the constant oscillation between the original and secondary meanings.

The increase in meaning of phraseological units is an unusual process that is carried out by various means and methods. Often, text (speech) authors use methods to change phraseological units from time to time - expanding component content and replacing phraseological unit components.

Occasional transformation allows quantitative description of signs and actions through language: quality and intensity of signs, duration, localization of processes, parametric signs of things and events.

Intensification is carried out by changing the component structure of the phraseological units, the component structure: the phraseological unit includes the occult component, additional semantics are added to the meaning of phraseological units, changes the details of the phraseological image. The analysis of the contexts in which the occasional variants of phraseological units work has revealed the following features of the processes of change of phraseological units, which, in turn, are determined by the specific

properties of the axial component-amplifiers.

In the dissertation "Complex transformations of phraseological units (in the material of twentieth-century English and American drama)" E.I. Khalatnikova considers double actualization as the third type of complex transformations of phraseological units. According to the researcher, the double actualization technique arises as a result of the application of one or more variable variations of phraseological units, leading to a literal interpretation of the meaning of the phraseological unit.

E.F. In her monograph, Arsentyeva focuses on the important role of the phraseological word in creating a humorous effect, as a result of which the contextual use of phraseological units becomes very common in jokes and anecdotes. The monograph presents the views of E. Kurganov, a specialist in literary anecdotes. The special construction of the anecdote leads to the conclusion that extraordinary dynamism and conflict largely determine the law of points, viz. a mechanism to recall the

beginning of the text and give it a completely different color. Simultaneous application of both direct and figurative phraseological meaning, playing with metaphor, is one of the most common ways to implement the law of points. An analysis of our material has shown that the most common type of contextual change of phraseological units is component / component replacement, the essence of which is to change the lexical composition or structure of phraseological units, as mentioned above. Often the substituted components are synonymous or belong to the same thematic group.

Let's look at examples from English:

- 1) They had no sooner sat down to table than he went straight to the point.
- 2) "I never slept a wink all night for thinking of you", he said.

This enhances the emotional and expressive meaning of the phraseological unit; the response is ridiculed. The inversion technique is also used to emphasize a part of a sentence emotionally and semantically, reversing the meaning of the modified phraseological unit

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